

SYNTHESIS OF ALICYCLIC SYSTEMS RELATED TO STEROIDS. PART I

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As a preliminary to the synthesis of 12-keto-steroids, attempts towards the synthesis of a tricyclic compound containing B, C and D rings have been described.

Investigations described in the following pages deal with the exploratory work of somewhat varied nature with a view to finding out a general method for the synthesis of this type of alicyclic compounds incorporating the more salient features of the molecule. These pilot experiments are, however, limited to the building up of the fused system comprising B, C and D rings with the "C₁₃-methyl" group and the *iso*-octyl side-chain from simple cyclohexane and cyclopentane derivatives.

The main scheme of the work that has been originally chalked out may be depicted in the following manner :—

*iso*Hexyl iodide condenses smoothly with ethyl methylmalonate to give (I), which on hydrolysis and decarboxylation leads to the formation of (II) in a very good yield. The acid chloride of this reacts with diazomethane in ethereal solution and from the diazoketone, the bromoketone (III) is obtained on treatment with hydrobromic acid solution. This condenses smoothly with ethyl acetoacetate and the crude condensation product is hydrolysed with dilute alkali under the usual conditions with the expectation of obtaining the corresponding cyclopentene derivative (*Ber.*, 1939, 72, 1590; 1942, 78, 448), but the product actually isolated corresponds to the diketone (IV). The attempts so far made for the closing up of the ring have met with failure. Action of alkali of different concentrations or use of dry sodium ethoxide effects no improvement in the process. A similar failure has also been met with in the use of sulphuric acid of varying concentrations or anhydrous oxalic acid. It is rather curious to note that the closing up of the cyclopentene ring from 1 : 4-diketones is almost instantaneous, but in this case no useful product could be isolated.

Next, the following line of attack has been pursued which can be graphically represented below.

* A preliminary note appeared in the *Science & Culture*, 1943-44, 9, 505.

Here the *iso*-octyl residue has been dropped leaving therein the possibility of introducing it at a later stage. Methylcyclopentene has been oxidised in acetic anhydride solution with selenium dioxide (Dane, *Annalen*, 1937, **532**, 35) but the isolation of the acetate of 2-methyl- Δ^2 -cyclopentenol presents unusual difficulties. Consequently, the original process has been modified to the extent of extracting the acetate with ether and removing all acidic impurities by washing with a saturated solution of sodium carbonate. The acetate has been hydrolysed under the usual conditions and the ketonic impurity is removed by washing with a saturated solution of sodium bisulphite. The alcohol is obtained in a very poor yield, barely reaching 5% of the theory. It is, however, converted into the bromide which condenses smoothly with the potassium salt of cyclohexanone carboxylic ester to give (V). The ester is hydrolysed with baryta and the ketone (VI) is isolated in a very poor yield along with a considerable amount of the high boiling product. To avoid the process of alkaline hydrolysis, the actual course of reactions has been further modified along the following line:—

Cope (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1940, **62**, 441) has shown that the condensation of $\alpha\beta$ -unsaturated halides with ethyl alkylidene-cyanoacetate in presence of sodium takes place with the formation of $\beta\gamma$ -unsaturated cyano-ester. During distillation, the unsaturated alkyl groups migrate to the γ -position with regeneration of the $\alpha\beta$ -double bond in the substituted cyano-esters. From a detailed study of the various allied systems, the complete analogy, as well as the genetic relationship of this system with Claisen's rearrangement of phenolic ethers, has been established. The two systems can be represented thus:

Moreover, in the case of Claisen's rearrangement, Δ^2 -cyclohexenyl ether of phenol has been found to migrate to give 2- Δ^2 -cyclohexenyl phenol (Cornforth *et al.*, *J. Proc.*

Roy. Soc., N.S. Wales, 1938, **71**, 329). As expected; methylcyclopentenyl bromide condenses smoothly with ethyl cyclohexylidene-cyanoacetate under the specified conditions and the condensation product is isolated in a moderate yield with a wide boiling range. Unfortunately, the amount of the condensation product available is too insufficient to proceed with the scheme, and further work is moreover prohibited by the relative inaccessibility of the starting material. From stereochemical standpoint, it is of interest to note that in view of the later work of Linstead (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1938, 668) the reduction of (VIIb) with aluminium amalgam may lead to *trans*-configuration of acetic acid chain and ultimately to the *trans*-locking of the B/C rings.

Because of the difficulty of preparing substituted cyclopentene halides, it was thought desirable to reverse the process, *i.e.*, to condense properly substituted cyclohexane halides with simple or substituted cyclopentanone carboxylic esters. A preliminary study has been made with cyclohexyl bromide with which the reaction proceeds smoothly leading to the formation of ethyl 2-cyclohexylcyclopentanone-2-carboxylate (VIII), which on hydrolysis with hydrochloric acid gives the 2-cyclohexylcyclopentanone (IX) along with a highly crystalline solid.

Ethyl 2-bromocyclohexylacetate (X) has been prepared from the corresponding lactone, but this failed to condense with ethylcyclopentanone carboxylate, although there is copious separation of alkali bromide. The reaction might have proceeded with the elimination of hydrobromic acid with the regeneration of the unsaturated ester. In order to induce sufficient reactivity to the halogen atom with the simultaneous removal of the labile quaternary hydrogen atom, it was decided to introduce an unsaturation in the molecule in immediate vicinity of the bromine atom in (X). With that end in view, the following compounds (XIa or XIb) have been prepared through a series of reactions.

Ethyl cyclohexenylacetate readily adds up bromine which again loses hydrobromic acid on treatment with sodium methoxide. It appears that (XIb) is the most probable structure, for the reactivity of the halogen atom can be explained from the principle of vinylogy (*Fuson, Chem. Rev.*, 1935, **16**, 1).

The condensation product (XIa and/or XIb) undergoes catalytic hydrogenation smoothly to give (XIII). Attempts to hydrolyse it with hydrochloric acid are only

partially successful and so the Grignard's reaction is carried out on the keto-ester (XIII), and the hydroxy-ester is dehydrated with thionyl chloride and pyridine to give (XIV). The primary ester group of the unsaturated ester (XIV) is hydrolysed with methyl alcoholic potash and the free acid is converted into acid chloride, which on treatment with stannic chloride at low temperature gives a compound containing halogen in poor yield. Slightly low value of halogen content has been found on analysis and the ketonic group also could not be characterised by any well defined derivative. Attempts to close up the ring by heating the unsaturated acid with phosphorus pentoxide also did not meet with any notable success.

Preliminary experiments have also been carried out with ethyl 5-(1:6-dimethylhexyl)cyclopentanone-2-carboxylate (XVI), which has been prepared by Dieckmann's condensation of the corresponding diester (XV). The corresponding adipic acid has been prepared according to Rydon (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1939, 1546). The β -keto-ester (XVI) condenses smoothly with the unsaturated bromo-cyclohexylacetic ester (XIa or XIb) and the product so obtained is reduced catalytically to (XVII).

E X P E R I M E N T A L

Ethyl isoHexylmethylmalonate (I): *isoHexyl Iodide*.—The Grignard's complex, generated from magnesium (36 g.), *isoamyl iodide* (285 g.) in ether (400 c.c.) was treated in the cold with gaseous formaldehyde, generated from *paraformaldehyde* (63 g.) in the course of 2 hours. The complex was decomposed with a little more than twice the

theoretical amount of dilute sulphuric acid and ice. The alcohol was isolated by steam-distillation and purified from the unchanged halides by heating on the water-bath with freshly heated lime (10 g.). The alcohol passed over at 145°-150°, yield 90 g. This was converted into iodide by treatment with iodine (104 g.), red phosphorous (20 g.) and water (11 c.c.) and refluxing finally for 2 hours. It passed over at 166°-168°, yield 130 g.

Ethyl oxalopropionate was prepared through the condensation of ethyl oxalate with ethyl propionate in presence of sodium ethoxide which on distillation at ordinary pressure gave ethyl methylmalonate in a good yield with loss of carbon monoxide.

Ethyl methylmalonate was converted into the sodium salt by treating with finely divided metal (12.4 g.) under benzene (200 c.c.). *iso*Hexyl iodide (110 g.) was added and the mixture was refluxed on the water-bath for 12 hours and finally in the oil-bath for 10 hours. The desired product distilled at 122°-125°/7 mm., yield 105 g. (Found: C, 64.8; H, 9.8. $C_{14}H_{26}O_4$ requires C, 65.1; H, 10.1 per cent).

α,α-Dimethylheptioic Acid (II).—The above ester was dissolved in rectified spirit (120 c.c.) and to this was added potassium hydroxide (20 g.) in water (20 c.c.) and refluxed for 2 hours. The clear solution was diluted with water, and alcohol was removed on the steam-bath. The neutral matter was extracted with ether and the alkaline solution on acidification gave a crystalline product which was taken up in ether. On removal of the solvent, the residue was rapidly heated to 180°-190° so that the process of decarboxylation was complete within 15 minutes. The residue on distillation in vacuum passed over at 116°/6 mm., yield 21 g.

The acid chloride was prepared by treating the acid (27.5 g.) with PCl_5 (10 c.c.) in the cold. It was left overnight and then refluxed for 3 hours. The acid chloride was decanted off and on distillation it passed over at 79°/9 mm. as a clear, colourless liquid, yield 25 g. The amide, prepared by the interaction of the acid chloride and liquor ammonia, crystallised from dilute acetone, m.p. 96° (cf. Mukherjee, *Science & Culture*, 1941, 7, 59).

ω-Bromomethyl-(1:5-dimethylhexyl)-ketone (III).—The above acid chloride (38 g.) in ether (25 c.c.) was added with cooling to a solution of diazomethane, prepared from nitrosomethylurea (75 g.) in dry ether (500 c.c.). After standing in the cold for an hour, hydrobromic acid (50 c.c., 48%) was slowly added to the yellow solution with constant shaking, when a vigorous evolution of nitrogen took place. The mixture was allowed to stand overnight. The ethereal solution was then washed with water and dilute sodium carbonate solution and dried. On distillation, the bromo-ketone (50.5 g.) was obtained boiling at 103°/9 mm. (cf. Mukherjee, *loc. cit.*). (Found: Br, 33.68. $C_{10}H_{19}OBr$ requires Br, 34.04 per cent).

2-*iso*Hexylheptan-3:6-dione (IV).—Freshly distilled ethyl acetoacetate (21 g.) was added dropwise to a suspension of finely divided sodium (3.4 g.) under ether at 0°. The sodio-salt was cooled further and to this was added the above bromo-ketone (35 g.) dissolved in ether. The product was allowed to stand for 2 days and then refluxed for 4 hours at 50°-55°. It was acidified and extracted with ether, dried and the solvent removed on the water-bath and finally under reduced pressure. The residue, thus obtained, was heated with caustic soda solution (1500 c.c., 2%) at 60° for 5 hours. Next, it was boiled for 10 minutes and on cooling it was extracted thrice with ether.

The alkaline solution was next acidified with hydrochloric acid and warmed on the wire-gauge for 10 minutes until the evolution of gas slackened. On cooling, it was extracted with ether and the ethereal extract was washed with alkali and dried and distilled. The diketone passed over at 122° - $127^{\circ}/6$ mm. as a clear, colourless oil having a characteristic smell, yield 21 g. (Found: C, 74.1, 74.2; H, 10.9, 11.1. $C_{13}H_{24}O_2$ requires C 73.6; H, 11.3 per cent).

2-(2'-Methyl- Δ^2 -cyclopentenyl)-2-carbethoxycyclopentanone (V).—*2-Methyl- Δ^2 -cyclopentenol* was prepared in a very poor yield from methylcyclopentene by oxidation with selenium dioxide in acetic anhydride solution and subsequent hydrolysis with alkali. The alcohol (5 g.) was diluted with four times its volume of CS_2 and the mixture was thoroughly cooled in ice. PBr_3 (2.5 c.c.) was added dropwise when the solution assumed a deep green colour. It was kept in an ice-chest overnight and then decomposed with ice. Finally the bromide was isolated, b.p. 67° - $75^{\circ}/20$ mm., yield 4 g. It had a characteristic smell producing tears and it rapidly polymerised turning green, and consequently it was immediately used for the next operation.

Ethyl cyclohexanone carboxylate (6 g.) was converted into the potassium salt from potassium (1.1 g.) under xylene and on cooling, the above bromide was added. At first, it was heated on the water-bath for 3 hours and then refluxed in an oil-bath for 7 hours. It was decomposed with water and extracted with ether. On removal of the solvent, the residue was distilled when practically the whole of it came at 130° - $135^{\circ}/4$ mm., yield 4.5 g. (Found: C, 71.6; H, 8.7. $C_{12}H_{22}O_2$ requires C, 72.0; H, 8.8 per cent).

2-(2'-Methyl- Δ^2 -cyclopentenyl)cyclohexanone (VI).—The above product (6 g.) was refluxed with baryta (18 g.), dissolved in distilled water (80 c.c.) for 14 hours. It was cooled and acidified with hydrochloric acid and extracted with ether. After removal of the ether, the residue was distilled in vacuum. A fraction (1 g.) was collected boiling at 115° - $125^{\circ}/7$ mm. and another fraction (2 g.) came over at 215° - $225^{\circ}/9$ mm., which was highly viscous. The latter was not further investigated and the former on distillation, gave the following data, and it was the desired product. (Found: C, 80.2; H, 9.7. $C_{12}H_{18}O$ requires C, 80.8; H, 10.1 per cent).

Ethyl (2'-Methyl- Δ^2 -cyclopentenyl)- Δ^1 -cyclohexenyl-cyanoacetate (VIIa) and/or *Ethyl 2-(2'-Methyl- Δ^2 -cyclopentenyl)-cyclohexylidene-cyanoacetate* (VIIb).—Ethyl cyclohexylidene-cyanoacetate was prepared through the condensation of ethyl cyanoacetate with cyclohexanone in presence of ammonium acetate, glacial acetic acid and benzene. Sodium (5 g.) was dissolved in dry isopropyl alcohol (25 c.c.) and to this solution, cooled in a freezing mixture, was added ethyl cyclohexylidene-cyanoacetate (4 g.) followed by methylcyclopentenyl bromide (2.4 g.). The mixture was refluxed on the water-bath for 4 hours and in the oil-bath for 6 hours. The product on dilution with water was extracted with ether and the residue, left after evaporation of the solvent, boiled over a wide range, and the fraction passing over at 180° - $200^{\circ}/7$ mm. was collected, yield 3 g. (Found: N, 5.8. $C_{17}H_{25}O_2N$ requires N, 5.2 per cent).

Ethyl 2-cyclohexylcyclopentanone-2-carboxylate (VIII).—To the potassium salt of ethyl cyclopentanone carboxylate, prepared from ethyl cyclopentanone carboxylate (16 g.) and potassium (4 g.) under xylene (30 c.c.) was added cyclohexyl bromide (18 g.) and the mixture was refluxed in an oil-bath for 8 hours. On working up the reaction

mixture a product was obtained boiling at 140° - $150^{\circ}/8$ mm. which gave no ferric chloride reaction in alcoholic solution, yield 17 g. A considerable tarry matter remained in the flask. (Found: C, 66.4; H, 8.9. $C_{14}H_{22}O_2$ requires C, 66.3; H, 9.4 per cent).

2-cyclohexylcyclopentanone (IX).—The above ester (5 g.) was heated in a sealed tube with hydrochloric acid (conc., 20 c.c.) for 10 hours at 150° - 160° . On cooling, a needle shaped crystalline solid separated at the bottom (which was not appreciably soluble in ether) together with a dark oil on the surface. It was extracted with ether and the ethereal extract washed with sodium carbonate solution, dried and distilled when a small quantity of a very pleasant smelling liquid boiling at 105° - $107^{\circ}/7$ mm. was obtained, yield 1.5 g. (Found: C, 78.9; H, 10.4. $C_{11}H_{18}O$ requires C, 79.5; H 10.8 per cent). *Semicarbazone*, m.p. 207° .

Ethyl 2-Bromocyclohexylacetate (X).—The Reformatsky reaction-product from cyclohexanone and ethyl bromoacetate was dehydrated in the usual way and the β -unsaturated ester was lactonised by refluxing with dilute sulphuric acid (25%) for 2 days. The lactone passed over at 130 - $135^{\circ}/10$ mm. (cf. Ghose, *Science & Culture*, 1935, 1, 299). The lactone (12 g.) was treated with PBr₃ (50 g.) in the cold when a clear solution was obtained and it was allowed to stand overnight. Next it was poured into absolute alcohol (100 c.c.) and the mixture heated on the water-bath for an hour. On working up the reaction product, a pleasant smelling liquid was obtained, b.p. 125° - $132^{\circ}/8$ mm., yield 11 g. (Found: Br, 31.7. $C_{10}H_{17}O_2$ Br requires Br, 32.6 per cent).

Ethyl 2-Bromocyclohexylidene-acetate (XIa) and/or *Ethyl 6-Bromo- Δ' -cyclohexynylacetate* (XIb).—Ethyl Δ' -cyclohexynylacetate (40 g.) was dissolved in dry ether (120 c.c.) and cooled in a freezing mixture and the solution was thoroughly shaken. Bromine (13 c.c.) was gradually added and when the colour of bromine had disappeared, it was gradually treated with a cooled solution of sodium (5.5 g.) in methyl alcohol (75 c.c.). After addition was complete, stirring was continued for half-an-hour more. The mixture was decomposed with ice and extracted with ether. The residue after evaporation of the solvent was slowly distilled in vacuum. Two fractions were collected. The first fraction passed over at 110° - $120^{\circ}/5$ mm. (40 g.) and the second fraction at 130° - $140^{\circ}/3$ mm. (18 g.). The second fraction was a very heavy liquid and it was dissolved in dry ether (20 c.c.) and cooled in ice and again treated with sodium methoxide solution, prepared from sodium (1.2 g.) and methyl alcohol (20 c.c.). On working up this product, the desired monobromo-ester passed over at 110° - $115^{\circ}/4$ mm. These two fractions were combined and on redistillation the desired product was obtained, b.p. $122^{\circ}/7$ mm., yield 50 g. (Found: Br, 31.9. $C_{10}H_{16}O_2$ Br requires Br, 32.4 per cent).

Ethyl 2-(1'-Carbethoxy-2'-ketocyclopentyl)-cyclohexylidene-acetate (XIIa) and/or *Ethyl 6-(1'-Carbethoxy-2'-ketocyclopentyl)- Δ' -cyclohexynylacetate* (XIIb).—Potassium salt of ethyl cyclopentanone carboxylate, prepared from the ester (32 g.) and potassium (7 g.) under xylene, was treated with the above bromo-ester (45 g.) and refluxed in an oil-bath for 6 hours. The brown solution was decomposed with water and extracted with a further quantity of xylene. On removal of the solvent, a light yellow oil was collected at 195° - $200^{\circ}/10$ mm., which on redistillation passed over at 176° - $180^{\circ}/4$ mm., yield 28 g. (Found: C, 66.7; H, 7.98. $C_{18}H_{26}O_3$ requires C, 67.1; H, 8.07 per cent).

Ethyl 2-(1'-Carbethoxy-2'-ketocyclopentyl)-cyclohexylacetate (XIII).—The above ester (20 g.) was reduced with platinum catalyst (0.2 g.) in glacial acetic acid solution. The theoretical quantity of hydrogen was taken up in course of 2 days and the catalyst had to be activated once. On distillation, a clear, colourless oil boiling at 165° - $170^{\circ}/3$ mm. was collected, yield 18 g. (Found: C, 66.7; H, 8.4. $C_{18}H_{28}O_4$ requires C, 66.6; H, 8.6 per cent).

Ethyl 2-(1'-Carbethoxy-2'-methyl- Δ^2 -cyclopentenyl)-cyclohexylacetate (XIV).—The Grignard's complex, prepared from magnesium (1.6 g., 1.3 mols.) and methyl iodide (5 c.c.) and dry ether (50 c.c.) was added with stirring to the above keto-ester (12 g.), dissolved in ether (100 c.c.) and cooled in a freezing mixture. A gummy mass separated out and it was allowed to stand for half-an-hour in the cold. On decomposing the gummy product with ice-cold sulphuric acid, it was worked up in the usual way and finally distilled, when a thick oil boiling at 170° - $178^{\circ}/4$ mm. was obtained. It possessed a camphoraceous smell and turned brown on standing. For complete dehydration, the above hydroxy-ester (9 g.) was taken up in ether (20 c.c.) and pyridine (3 g.) was added. On cooling in a freezing mixture, thionyl chloride (1.7 c.c.) was added gradually. At the end of 2 hours, dry ether (25 c.c.) was added and it was allowed to stand overnight, and finally decomposed with ice. On extraction with ether and washing the ethereal extract with acid and alkali, the unsaturated ester was obtained boiling at 170° - $177^{\circ}/4$ mm. which contained dissolved sulphur. It was dissolved in dry benzene and boiled with freshly precipitated copper for 2 hours to remove sulphur and the desired ester was obtained boiling at 168° - $173^{\circ}/4$ mm. as a light yellow oil. (Found: C, 70.2; H, 8.4. $C_{19}H_{28}O_4$ requires C, 70.6; H, 9.0 per cent).

Attempts towards ring-closure with Stannic Chloride on the Acid Chloride from the above Ester.—The above ester (7 g.) was hydrolysed with caustic potash (2.1 g.) in methyl alcohol (22 c.c.) and a little water. It was refluxed on the water-bath for 6 hours. Next it was diluted with water and heated on the water-bath to remove methyl alcohol. On removing neutral matter with ether, the free acid was isolated as a gummy mass (4.5 g.). It was thoroughly dried and dissolved in ether (25 c.c.) and treated with pyridine (1.5 c.c.) and thionyl chloride (1.2 c.c.). The excess of pyridine was removed by the addition of ethereal hydrogen chloride. On cooling in a freezing mixture, pyridine hydrochloride solidified and the upper layer was decanted off and the solvent removed, and the residue was dissolved in dry CS_2 (10 c.c.). Stannic chloride (2 c.c.) was dissolved in CS_2 (12 c.c.) and the solution was thoroughly cooled in a freezing mixture and to this was added the above acid chloride solution. A dark, red pasty mass separated and it was allowed to stand overnight. The CS_2 layer was separated and the solid residue was decomposed with ice and hydrochloric acid. It was extracted with ether and the ethereal extract washed with ice-cold caustic potash solution. On working up, a pleasant smelling liquid boiling at 140° - $145^{\circ}/3$ mm. was collected, yield 0.5 g. (Found: Cl, 8.9. $C_{17}H_{23}O_3Cl$ requires Cl, 11.4 per cent).

Ethyl α -(1:6-Dimethylhexyl)-adipate (XV).—The crude acidic product (20 g.), obtained through the hydrolysis of the substituted cyclopentanone carboxylic ester (48 g.) with baryta (105 g.) and water (300 c.c.) was thoroughly dried in vacuum and esterified with a mixture of alcohol (100 c.c.) and sulphuric acid (10 c.c.) on a boiling

water-bath for 12 hours. It was poured into water, extracted with ether and washed with sodium carbonate solution. On distillation, it passed over at 155° - $158^{\circ}/5$ mm., yield 16 g. (Found: C, 68.9. H, 10.4. $C_{18}H_{24}O_4$ requires C, 68.7; H, 10.8 per cent).

Ethyl 3-(1:6-Dimethylhexyl)-cyclopentan-2-one-1-carboxylate (XVI).—The above ester (15 g.) was treated with sodium dust (2.5 g.) in benzene (40 g.) and a few drops of alcohol. It was refluxed for 3 hours when the whole of sodium went into solution. On working up the reaction mixture, the fraction boiling at 140° - $145^{\circ}/3$ mm. was collected, yield 5 g. It gave a very beautiful violet ferric chloride coloration in alcoholic solution. Considerable quantities of a higher boiling residue remained in the flask. (Found: C, 72.1; H, 10.1. $C_{18}H_{28}O_3$ requires C, 71.6; H, 10.4 per cent).

Ethyl 2-(1'-Carbethoxy-2'-keto-3'-1:6-dimethylhexyl)cyclopentenylcyclohexylacetate (XVII).—The above ester (3 g.) was converted into potassium salt by treatment with potassium (0.5 g.) in xylene (10 c.c.) and the unsaturated bromo-ester (XIa, XIb, 5 g.) was added and immediately heated to reflux in an oil-bath. From the reaction mixture, a fraction boiling at 215 - $220^{\circ}/6$ mm. was collected, yield 3.5 g. (Found: C, 72.4; H, 9.1. $C_{28}H_{44}O_5$ requires C, 72.1; H, 9.4 per cent).

The above ester (2 g.) was reduced with Adam's catalyst (0.1 g.) in acetic acid solution, when hydrogen was absorbed very slowly and the reduced ester was isolated at 213° - $216^{\circ}/6$ mm., yield 1.4 g.

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